

Photochemical and thermal transformations of some diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes

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Abstract : Photochemical and thermal transformations of diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes to the exotic isomeric alkenes have been described. The products formation is exclusively controlled by the nature of substituents on the cyclopropane ring as well as on the aromatic ring in benzoyl group. The stimulus behind this is the thermostability of the intermediate 1,4-biradical produced photochemically which, in turn, control the product formation/distribution.

Keywords : Benzoylcyclopropanes, H-abstraction, photoirradiation, thermolysis.

Introduction

Cyclopropane ring, the smallest ring in organic compounds is an integral entity of a vast variety of naturally occurring compounds^{1,2}. Many potent pesticides, viz. pyrethrins and synthetic pyrethroids³ are the best known examples that belong to the class of cyclopropane derivatives. In the medical technologies, the halo-substituted cyclopropanes are regarded as the promising non-toxic anesthetics. A number of compounds in cyclopropane series have been tested for their pharmacological activity⁴ as depressants, analgesics and antifungal agents. The three-membered ring compounds as C-3 units have also been utilized as promising synthons for the development of a variety of new synthetic routes⁵. The cyclopropane ring has been figured out to possess σ -aromaticity^{6,7} that is responsible for its anomalous chemical properties like *cis-trans* isomerisations⁸⁻¹⁰, photorearrangements¹¹⁻¹³ including ring expansion, photoadditions, photocycloadditions^{14,15}, photooxygenations¹⁶ and fragmentations¹⁷. The main photochemical behavior of cyclopropane itself and its derivatives such as alkyl substituted cyclopropanes in the gas phase¹⁸⁻²⁰, in solution^{21,22} (< 200 nm light) and in a matrix^{23,24} is the fragmentation to alkenes and carbenes. It has been found that the benzoylcyclopropanes undergo the ring cleavage to produce exclusively α,β -unsaturated ketone with homolytic cleavage of the cyclopropyl bond β - to the carbonyl group followed by

the 1,2-hydrogen shift to give α,β -unsaturated ketones. The benzoylcyclopropanes²⁵ also yield isomeric alkenes photochemically.

Keeping in view the important uses and interesting reactions elicited by cyclopropanes, in this communication, we report the results of our investigations pertaining to the photochemical and thermal transformations of some diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes bearing different substituents both on cyclopropane as well as on benzoyl group with a view of comparing and contrasting the reactions of these 3-membered ring compounds from the excited and the ground states. The introduction of carbonyl group as a benzoyl moiety on cyclopropane ring in the present molecules generates a bichromophoric system which may absorb light well above 200 nm that encouraged us to investigate the photolytic and thermal behavior of the cyclopropanes. These specially designed molecules are also endowed with another exclusive feature of possessing a suitably placed H-atom that may be easily abstracted through Norrish type-II process²⁶⁻²⁸, an important tool for the synthesis of complex molecules and may result in the formation of triplet biradicals to ensue various inherent reactions. Additionally, here the cyclopropane ring and C=O group both being chromophores, may participate either in isolation or in conjugation with each other in photochemical reactions.

Results and discussion

The required diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes **6a-d** and **11a-d** were synthesized by alkylation of diethylmalonate through the following sequence of reactions (Scheme 1).

The compound **5** in its IR spectrum exhibited a strong absorption band at 2238 cm^{-1} that may be assigned to the cyano ($-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) group. A 300 MHz ^1H NMR spectrum showed a dd at δ 1.28 (1H, $J_{1,3a}$ 6.6 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.8 Hz) that was assigned to H-1 of cyclopropane ring. The proton $\text{H}_a\text{-3}$ and $\text{H}_b\text{-3}$ signal appeared as dd at δ 1.03 and

The IR spectrum of compound **6a**, obtained from compound **5** by treating with the Grignard reagent followed by aq. AcOH, showed two absorptions at 1665 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) and 1015 cm^{-1} (cyclopropane) confirming benzoyl-cyclopropane moiety. The 300 MHz ^1H NMR spectrum in aromatic region showed peaks at δ 7.94 (2H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.1, 7.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.48 (1H, tt, $J_{m,o}$ 2.1, 7.5 Hz, H-4'), 7.39 (3H, dt, $J_{m,o}$ 2.1, 7.5 Hz, H-3',5') consistent to benzoyl group. The cyclopropane ring protons were located at δ 2.61 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.8 Hz, H-1),

(i) $\text{R}'_2\text{C}=\text{CRCH}_2\text{X}/\text{NaH}/\text{dry THF}$; (ii) $\text{LiAlH}_4/\text{dry THF}$; (iii) $p\text{-TsCl}/\text{pyridine}/0^\circ\text{C}$; (iv) $\text{KCN}/\text{ethylene glycol}$; (v) $\text{R}''\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-MgX}/\text{dry ether}/\text{N}_2\text{ atm}$; (vi) $\text{AcOH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Scheme 1. Synthesis of diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes.

0.81 respectively with J_{gem} 5.1 Hz. The two singlets at δ 1.65 (3H) and 1.71 (3H) were assigned to $2'\text{-CH}_3$ and $2''\text{-CH}_3$ of allyl group. The signal of proton $\text{H}_a\text{-1}'$ was a doublet at δ 2.20 (J_{gem} 15.0 Hz) due to geminal coupling with $\text{H}_b\text{-1}'$.

Similarly, the peak due to $\text{H}_b\text{-1}'$ was also observed as doublet at δ 2.01. The two methylene protons of C-1'' were observed as two merged doublets between δ 2.36–2.42 due to deshielding by the cyano group. In the midfield region, four singlets at δ 4.67, 4.75, 4.80 and 4.82 were assigned to $\text{H}_b\text{-3}'$, $\text{H}_b\text{-3}''$, $\text{H}_a\text{-3}'$ and $\text{H}_a\text{-3}''$ respectively based on their relative position with respect to the cyano group. This type of spectral data was used to establish the structure of compound **10** also.

1.64 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{3a,3b}$ 4.2 Hz, $\text{H}_a\text{-3}$) and 1.07 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.8 Hz, $J_{3b,3a}$ 4.2 Hz, $\text{H}_b\text{-3}$). These assignments were based on the *cis/trans* disposition of $\text{H}_a\text{-3}$ and $\text{H}_b\text{-3}$ with respect to benzoyl group and the J values ($J_{\text{cis}} > J_{\text{trans}}$). The protons $1'''\text{-CH}_2$ and $1''\text{-CH}_2$ were observed as multiplet at δ 2.17. The four singlets at δ 4.79, 4.70, 4.65 and 4.60 were assigned to $\text{H}_a\text{-3}'''$, $\text{H}_b\text{-3}'''$, $\text{H}_a\text{-3}''$ and $\text{H}_b\text{-3}''$ respectively. The $2'''\text{-CH}_3$ and $2''\text{-CH}_3$ protons were located at δ 1.70 and 1.56 as two singlets integrating for three protons each. The structures of other compounds (**6b-d** and **11a-d**) were likewise established.

The methanolic solution of benzoyl cyclopropanes (0.001 mol) was photoirradiated for 2 h with pyrex fil-

tered light in Srinivasan-Griffin photoreactor under nitrogen atmosphere. On chromatographic work up, the photolysates of **6a**, **6b**, **11a** and **11b** furnished the alkenes **12a**, **12b**, **13a** and **13b** respectively in the form of a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-alkenes which could not be separated but analyzed by ^1H NMR integral ratio of H-1". But, the substrates with methoxy group on the benzoyl moiety (i.e. **6c**, **6d**, **11c** and **11d**) did not undergo any photocleavage to the corresponding alkenes but did so upon thermolysis (Scheme 2). The plausible reason for this may be that in these compounds due to the introduction of methoxy group, a strong electron releasing group, the π - π^* triplet which is lower in energy becomes more important than that of n - π^* triplet thus inhibiting any detectable photoreaction occurring through H-abstraction^{29,30}. The thermolytic behavior of benzoylcyclopropanes was also studied at 160 °C in silicone oil bath for 7 min which provided a mixture that consisted of starting compound and their respective cleaved products i.e. *E*- and *Z*-isomeric alkenes.

isomers *E*- and *Z*- of alkene **12a**. The aromatic region of the spectrum was identical to that of starting cyclopropane **6a** with δ values at 7.88 (H-2',6'), 7.49 (H-4') and 7.39 (H-3',5'). Next to aromatic region the peaks at δ 5.78 and 5.70 (1H) were assigned to H-5 of *E*- and *Z*-isomer respectively. In the midfield region of spectrum, absorptions at δ 4.90 and 4.86 were assigned to H_a-7 proton of *E*- and *Z*-isomer respectively. The other signals at δ 4.83, 4.79 and 4.76 were due to H_b-7, H_a-3" and H_b-3" of both isomers. The ratio of *E*- and *Z*-isomer was calculated on the basis of integration of peak at δ 2.72 (2H, s, *Z*-isomer) and δ 2.89 (2H, s, *E*-isomer) of H-1". The other protons were revealed at δ 3.04 (2H, t, H-2, *E*), 2.99 (2H, t, H-2, *Z*), 2.39 (2H, t, H-3, *E*), 2.54 (2H, t, H-3, *Z*), 1.76 (3H, s, 6-CH₃, *E*), 1.73 (3H, s, 6-CH₃, *Z*), 1.65 (3H, s, 2"-CH₃, *E*) and 1.63 (3H, s, 2"-CH₃, *Z*).

The most incredible feature of ^1H NMR spectra of the products is the presence of two distinct doublets at δ 2.72 and δ 2.89 in compounds **12a-d** and at δ 2.82 and δ 2.92

Scheme 2. Photochemical and thermal irradiation of 2,2-diallylbenzoylcyclopropanes.

Remarkably, the structures of the products formed were found to be consistent with their spectral parameters (*vide* Experimental). These compounds in their IR spectra exhibited a strong absorption band in the region of 1681–1684 cm⁻¹ indicating the cleavage of cyclopropane ring. A 300 MHz ^1H NMR spectrum showed two

in compounds **13a-d**, that were assigned to H-1" of *Z*- and *E*-isomer respectively. The integration ratio of these protons was used to calculate isomeric ratio of *E/Z* alkenes.

Regarding mechanistic considerations, the formation of products upon photoirradiation can be rationalized

Scheme 3. Mechanism of formation of alkene from 2,2-diallylbenzoylcyclopropanes.

through the participation of C=O group which on $n-\pi^*$ excitation abstracts hydrogen from allylic $-\text{CH}_2-$ and results in generation of 1,4-biradical (A) that ultimately leads to the formation of alkene (*E*- and *Z*-isomers). Alternatively, the formation of alkene could be through direct cleavage of cyclopropane to form 1,3-biradical (B)

which on 1,2-hydrogen migration could give the same products. But, progressively decreased reaction yields on changing the $-\text{R}''$ from $\text{H} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 \rightarrow \text{OCH}_3$ clearly evinces the participation of C=O group and thus indicates the existence of mechanism A.

A deep insight through Table 1 clearly indicates that

Table 1. Percent cleavage of cyclopropane ring and *E/Z* ratio of alkene in photochemical reaction

R''	2,2-Bis(2-methylallyl)			2,2-Bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)		
	Compound	% cleavage	<i>E/Z</i> ratio	Compound	% cleavage	<i>E/Z</i> ratio
-H	6a	60	1 : 1	11a	62	1.4 : 1
$-\text{CH}_3$	6b	52	1.1 : 1	11b	41	1.5 : 1
$-\text{OCH}_3(m)$	6c	0	-	11c	0	-
$-\text{OCH}_3(p)$	6d	0	-	11d	0	-

Table 2. Percent cleavage of cyclopropane ring and *E/Z* ratio of alkene in thermal reaction

R''	2,2-Bis(2-methylallyl)			2,2-Bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)		
	Compound	%cleavage	<i>E/Z</i> ratio	Compound	%cleavage	<i>E/Z</i> ratio
-OCH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	6c	53	2.2 : 1	11c	95	3.3 : 1
-H	6a	52	2.0 : 1	11a	95	3.5 : 1
-CH ₃	6b	42	2.0 : 1	11b	95	3.9 : 1
-OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	6d	35	2.3 : 1	11d	95	4.0 : 1

the group -R'' does not have a perceptible effect on *E/Z* ratio of alkene but determines cleavage efficiency of cyclopropane. The *E/Z* ratio is predominantly affected by the 2,2-diallyl group which in turn has no effect on the cleavage efficiency of cyclopropane. Here, the replacement of 2,2-bis(2-methylallyl) group (**6a-b**) by 2,2-bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl) group (**11a-b**) increases the *E/Z* ratio of alkenes.

An examination of Table 2 shows that in thermal transformation also the substituent -R'' as well as 2-allyl group influences the product formation in a similar fashion as in photochemical reaction. In fact, their effect is more prominent in case of thermolysis as compared to photoirradiation (Table 1). The only assignable reason to this observation could be that in photochemical reaction, *cis-trans* isomerisation of the initially formed products takes place to set equilibrium through phantom state³¹⁻³³ that determines the *E/Z* ratio.

Remarkably, the structures of the products formed were found to be consistent with their spectral parameters (*vide* Experimental). The compounds (**12a-d** and **13a-d**) in their IR spectra exhibited a strong absorption band in the region of 1681–1684 cm⁻¹ indicating the cleavage of cyclopropane ring. The ¹H NMR spectra displayed the presence of two distinct doublets at δ 2.72 and δ 2.89 in compounds **12a-d** and at δ 2.82 and δ 2.92 in compounds **13a-d**, that were assigned to H-1'' of *Z*- and *E*-isomer respectively. The integration ratio of these protons was used to calculate isomeric ratio of *E/Z* alkenes.

Conclusion

Thus, in the present article, the endeavor has been made to investigate the photochemical and thermal transformation of diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropane to isomeric alkenes. It is concluded that H-abstraction from allylic -CH₂- by C=O group by Norrish type-II process is the

preferred pathway for the formation of the photoproducts. Study of effect of different substituents on product formation and distribution has explored that the inclusion of electron releasing group on the benzoyl moiety retards the product formation. The *E/Z* ratio of alkenes produced thermally was found to be predominant over that of photoirradiation process.

Experimental

General :

IR spectra were recorded on a Buck Scientific 500 spectrometer using KBr pellets. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on 300 MHz Bruker spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The photoirradiation of the deaerated solution of substrates was carried out in Srinivasan-Griffin photoreactor using a pyrex filter under nitrogen atmosphere. The columns for chromatographic separation were packed in pet. ether with silica gel.

Synthesis of 2,2-bis(2-methylallyl)diethylmalonate **2** :

To a hexane washed suspension of sodium hydride (50%, 24 g, 0.5 mol) in dry THF (200 ml) was added diethylmalonate (32 g, 0.2 mol) dropwise and this mixture was allowed to stir for 30 min. Thereafter, 3-chloro-2-methylpropene (39.6 g, 0.44 mol) was added and then the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h, decomposed by ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed 3–4 times with cold water, dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and the solvent evaporated to get 2,2-di(2-methylallyl)diethylmalonate **2**.

Yield 65%, clear liquid; b.p. 170–172 °C at 20 mm of Hg; ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) : 1648.5 (C=C), 1731 (C=O); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 4.77 (2H, q, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, H_a-3'), 4.67 (2H, t, J_{allyl} 0.9 Hz, H_b-3'), 4.11 (4H, q, $J_{1'',2''}$ 7.2 Hz, H-1''), 2.67 (4H, s, H-1''), 1.62 (6H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 2'-CH₃),

1.18 (6H, t, $J_{2'',1''}$ 7.2 Hz, H-2'').

Synthesis of 2,2-bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)diethylmalonate 7 :

The compound **7** was also synthesized by above procedure by using 1-bromo-3-methylbut-2-ene (65.56 g, 0.44 mol) in place of 3-chloro-2-methylpropene.

Yield 82%, colorless liquid; b.p. 180 °C at 20 mm of Hg; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1732 (C=O), 1609 (C=C); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 4.96 (2H, qt, $J_{2',1'}$ 7.5 Hz, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, H-2'), 4.15 (4H, q, $J_{1'',2''}$ 7.2 Hz, H-1''), 2.58 (4H, d, $J_{1',2'}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1'), 1.74 (6H, s, 3'-CH₃), 1.68 (6H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, H-4'), 1.24 (6H, t, $J_{2'',1''}$ 7.2 Hz, H-2'').

Synthesis of 2,2-bis(2-methylallyl)propane-1,3-diol 3 :

To a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (5.7 g, 0.15 mol) in well-dried THF (100 ml) was added dialkyldiethylmalonate **2** (26.8 g, 0.1 mol) dropwise with stirring and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h. It was cooled and poured onto crushed ice slowly which was subsequently neutralised with dil. HCl. The clear solution so obtained was extracted with ethylacetate, dried over anhyd. MgSO₄ and the solvent was distilled-off to get the 1,3-diol **3**.

Yield 55%, colorless solid; m.p. 138–140 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1644 (C=C), 3418 (OH); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 4.79 (2H, q, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, H_a-3'), 4.72 (2H, s, H_b-3'), 3.50 (4H, s, H-1, H-3), 1.98 (4H, s, H-1'), 1.94 (2H, br s, 1,3-OH), 1.63 (6H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 2'-CH₃).

Synthesis of 2,2-bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)propane-1,3-diol 8 :

The diol **8** was also synthesized taking diethyldiallylmalonate **7** as substrate by the same procedure as employed for 1,3-diol **3**.

Yield 62%, white solid; m.p. 72–75 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1674.4 (C=C), 3378 (OH); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 5.11 (2H, qt, $J_{2',1'}$ 7.5 Hz, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, H-2'), 3.51 (4H, s, H-1,3), 1.94 (4H, d, $J_{1',2'}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1'), 1.81 (2H, br s, 1,3-OH), 1.65 (6H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 3'-CH₃), 1.56 (6H, s, H-4').

Synthesis of 2,2-bis(2-methylallyl)propane-1,3-ditosylate 4 :

To a well-stirred solution of the diol **3** (9.2 g, 0.05 mol) in dry pyridine at 0 °C was added slowly a cold solution of *p*-toluene sulphonylchloride (20.9 g, 0.11 mol

in 20 ml of pyridine). The mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 2 h and then stirred overnight at room temperature. The solution was poured onto crushed ice and stirred well till solidification. The solid obtained was filtered and crystallized from acetone-water mixture (3 : 1) to give the colorless ditosylate **4**.

Yield 60%, colorless solid; m.p. 84–85 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1647 (C=C), 1097, 1183 (symm. S=O), 1362, 1458 (asymm. S=O); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 7.76 (1H, dd, $J_{\text{m,o}}$ 1.5, 8.1 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.37 (4H, d, $J_{\text{m,o}}$ 1.5, 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 4.85 (2H, q, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, H_a-3'), 4.61 (2H, s, H_b-3'), 3.85 (4H, s, H-1,3), 2.48 (6H, s, 4''-CH₃), 2.10 (4H, s, H-1'), 1.66 (6H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 2'-CH₃).

Synthesis of 2,2-bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)propane-1,3-ditosylate 9 :

The ditosylate **9** was also prepared from diol **8** by using the procedure used for the the synthesis of ditosylate **4**.

Yield 64%, colorless solid; m.p. 47–49 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1672 (C=C), 1097, 1184 (symm. S=O), 1363, 1462 (asymm. S=O); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 7.67 (4H, d, J_{o} 8.4 Hz, H-2'',6''), 7.28 (4H, d, J_{o} 8.4 Hz, H-3'',5''), 4.72 (2H, t, $J_{2',1'}$ 7.8 Hz, H-2'), 3.66 (4H, s, H-1,3), 2.39 (6H, s, 4''-CH₃), 1.82 (4H, d, $J_{1',2'}$ 7.8 Hz, H-1'), 1.53 (6H, s, 3'-CH₃), 1.44 (6H, s, H-4').

Synthesis of 1-cyano-2,2-bis(2-methylallyl)cyclopropane 5 :

To a suspension of ditosylate **4** already prepared (0.025 mol) in ethylene glycol (100 ml) was added potassium cyanide (4.87 g, 0.075 mol). The reaction mixture was heated on an oil bath at 90 °C for 30 min and the color of the reaction mixture turned dark brown. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 190 °C for 2 h and subsequently distilled to get 50 ml of distillate. The distillate consisted of two layers and was extracted with hexane (4 × 25 ml). The extracted hexane fractions were combined, washed with water, dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and solvent was removed on water bath. The viscous liquid left was percolated over a column of silica gel (100–200 mesh) to give a clear liquid of 1-cyano-2,2-bis(2-methylallyl)cyclopropane **5**.

Yield 40%, colorless liquid; b.p. 175–178 °C; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}) : 1650 (C=C), 2238 (C≡N), 1058 (cyclopropane);

δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 4.82 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.80 (1H, s, H_a-3'), 4.75 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 4.67 (1H, s, H_b-3'), 2.36–2.42 (2H, two merged doublets, J_{gem} 11.2 Hz, H_a-1'', H_b-1''), 2.20 (1H, d, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_a-1'), 2.01 (1H, d, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_b-1'), 1.71 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃), 1.67 (3H, s, 2'-CH₃), 1.28 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 6.6 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.8 Hz, H-1), 1.03 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 5.1 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 6.6 Hz, H_a-3), 0.81 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 5.1 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.8 Hz, H_b-3).

Synthesis of 1-cyano-2,2-bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)cyclopropane 10 :

The 1-cyano-2,2-bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)cyclopropane **10** was synthesized from ditosylate **9** by using procedure as used for the synthesis of 1-cyano-2,2-bis(2-methylallyl)cyclopropane **5**.

Yield 28%, colorless clear liquid; b.p. 184–188 °C; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 2238 (C≡N), 1617 (C=C), 1051 (cyclopropane); δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 5.14 (1H, td, $J_{2'',1''}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, H-2''), 4.80 (1H, td, $J_{2',1'}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, H-2'), 2.20 (1H, dd, J_{gem} 6.4 Hz, $J_{1''a,2''}$ 7.2 Hz, H_a-1''), 2.08 (1H, dd, J_{gem} 6.4 Hz, $J_{1''b,2''}$ 7.2 Hz, H_b-1''), 2.02 (1H, dd, $J_{1'a,2'}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{gem} 14.7 Hz, H_a-1'), 1.92 (1H, dd, $J_{1'b,2'}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{gem} 15.5 Hz, H_b-1'), 1.67 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 3''-CH₃), 1.63 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.52 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, 3'-CH₃), 1.40 (3H, s, H-4'), 1.15 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.4 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.8 Hz, H-1), 0.92 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.4 Hz, $J_{3a,3b}$ 5.4 Hz, H_a-3), 0.85 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 5.4 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.8 Hz, H_b-3).

Synthesis of substituted diallyl-benzoylcyclopropanes 6a-d and 11a-d :

To a suspension of dry magnesium turnings (480 mg, 0.02 mol) and iodine in dry ether (50 ml) was added bromobenzene (3.1 g, 0.02 mol) under N₂ atm. with vigorous stirring. After 30 min (when all Mg got consumed) to this reaction mixture was added cyclopropanenitrile **5** (1.75 g, 0.01 mol) slowly followed by refluxing for 3 h. Reaction mixture was decomposed with 10% aq. AcOH. The organic layer was extracted with ether and washed with water 3–4 times. It was dried over anhydrous MgSO₄ and solvent was removed under vacuum. The brown liquid obtained was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (200–400 mesh) packed in petroleum ether to get pure **6a**.

The other diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes **6b-d** and **11a-d** were synthesized by this procedure from

cyclopropanenitrile **5** and **10** respectively by reacting them with appropriate bromoarene.

1-Benzoyl-2,2-bis(2-methylallyl)cyclopropane 6a :

Yield 38%, colorless liquid; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 1665 (C=O), 1599 (C=C), 1015 (cyclopropane); UV (λ_{max} , MeOH) : 240.5, 260, 267, 303 nm; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 7.94 (2H, dd, J_{m} 2.1 Hz, J_{o} 7.5 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.48 (1H, tt, J_{m} 2.1 Hz, J_{o} 7.5 Hz, H-4'), 7.39 (2H, dt, J_{m} 2.1 Hz, J_{o} 7.5 Hz, H-3',5'), 4.79 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.70 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 4.65 (1H, s, H_a-3'), 4.61 (1H, s, H_b-3'), 2.61 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.8 Hz, H-1), 2.17 (4H, m, H-1'',1'''), 1.70 (3H, s, 2'''-CH₃), 1.64 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, H_a-3), 1.56 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃), 1.07 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.8 Hz, H_b-3); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CDCl₃) : 198.10 (C=O), 143.42 (C-2'''), 142.68 (C-2''), 138.74 (C-1'), 132.80 (C-4'), 128.47 (C-2',6'), 128.13 (C-3',5'), 113.41 (C-3'''), 112.25 (C-3''), 44.38 (C-1'''), 36.12 (C-1''), 32.16 (C-1), 29.29 (C-2), 23.52 (2'''-CH₃), 22.99 (2''-CH₃), 22.38 (C-3); Mass (*m/z*) : 254 (83%), 253 (30%), 199 (42%), 149 (18%), 132 (31%), 105 (100%), 77 (9%).

2,2-Bis(2-methylallyl)-1-(4'-methylbenzoyl)cyclopropane 6b :

Yield 35%, colorless liquid; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 1663 (C=O), 1607.9 (C=C), 1015 (cyclopropane); UV (λ_{max} , MeOH) : 240, 248, 255, 272 nm; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) : 7.84 (2H, d, J_{o} 8.1 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.19 (2H, d, J_{o} 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 4.79 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.73 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 4.65 (1H, s, H_a-3'), 4.60 (1H, s, H_b-3'), 2.59 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1), 2.35 (3H, s, 4'-CH₃), 2.17 (4H, br s, H-1'',1'''), 1.70 (3H, s, 2'''-CH₃), 1.62 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 3.9 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, H_a-3), 1.55 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃), 1.05 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 3.9 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.8 Hz, H_b-3); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CDCl₃) : 197.0 (C=O), 142.72 (C-2'''), 142.40 (C-2''), 141.96 (C-4'), 135.49 (C-1'), 128.36 (C-2',6'), 127.46 (C-3',5'), 112.53 (C-3'''), 112.39 (C-3''), 43.60 (C-1'''), 35.35 (C-1''), 31.03 (C-1), 28.34 (C-2), 22.71 (2'''-CH₃), 22.17 (2''-CH₃), 21.30 (C-3), 20.75 (4'-CH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 268 (98%), 267 (30%), 213 (55%), 149 (14%), 146 (29%), 119 (100%), 105 (24%), 91 (31%), 77 (8.5%).

2,2-Bis(2-methylallyl)-1-(3'-methoxybenzoyl)cyclopropane 6c :

Yield 35%, colorless liquid; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 1666 (C=O), 1596.5 (C=C), 1039 (cyclopropane); UV (λ_{max} ,

MeOH) : 225, 251, 271, 299 nm; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 7.62 (1H, td, $J_{\text{m},0}$ 1.5, 7.5 Hz, H-6'), 7.54 (1H, dd, J_{m} 1.5, 2.4 Hz, H-2'), 7.39 (1H, t, J_{o} 8.1 Hz, H-5'), 7.11 (1H, dd, J_{m} 2.4 Hz, J_{o} 8.1 Hz, H-4'), 4.88 (1H, s, H_a -3'''), 4.80 (1H, s, H_b -3'''), 4.75 (1H, s, H_a -3''), 4.70 (1H, s, H_b -3''), 3.87 (3H, s, 3'-OCH₃), 2.68 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1), 2.27 (4H, m, H-1''', 1''), 1.79 (3H, s, 2'''-CH₃), 1.64 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 3.9 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, H_a -3), 1.65 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃), 1.16 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 3.9 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.8 Hz, H_b -3); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CDCl_3) : 197.97 (C=O), 159.74 (C-3'), 143.41 (C-2'''), 142.67 (C-2''), 140.14 (C-1'), 129.42 (C-5'), 120.84 (C-6'), 119.0 (C-4'), 113.41 (C-2'), 112.46 (C-3'''), 112.26 (C-3''), 55.37 (3'-OCH₃), 44.36 (C-1'''), 36.15 (C-1''), 32.24 (C-1), 29.38 (C-2), 23.50 (2'''-CH₃), 22.96 (2''-CH₃), 22.50 (C-3); Mass (m/z) : 284 (77%), 283 (16%), 229 (49%), 163 (20%), 149 (10%), 135 (100%), 121 (14%), 107 (14%), 105 (18%), 77 (8.6%).

2,2-Bis(2-methylallyl)-1-(4'-methoxybenzoyl)cyclopropane 6d :

Yield 40%, colorless liquid; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1657.5 (C=O), 1027 (cyclopropane); UV (λ_{max} , MeOH) : 226, 251, 267, 288 nm; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 8.01 (2H, d, J_{o} 9.0 Hz, H-2', 6'), 6.97 (2H, d, J_{o} 9.0 Hz, H-3', 5'), 4.88 (1H, s, H_a -3'''), 4.79 (1H, s, H_b -3'''), 4.74 (1H, s, H_a -3''), 4.69 (1H, s, H_b -3''), 3.89 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 2.65 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.8 Hz, H-1), 2.27 (2H, br s, H-1'''), 2.23 (2H, br s, H-1''), 1.79 (3H, s, 2'''-CH₃), 1.62 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, H_a -3), 1.64 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃), 1.11 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.8 Hz, H_b -3); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CDCl_3) : 196.61 (C=O), 163.08 (4'), 143.56 (2'''), 142.81 (2''), 131.87 (C-1'), 130.35 (C-2', 6'), 113.19 (C-3', 5'), 113.27 (C-3'''), 112.16 (C-3''), 53.53 (4'-OCH₃), 44.41 (C-1'''), 36.20 (C-1''), 31.50 (C-1), 28.88 (C-2), 23.53 (2'''-CH₃), 22.95 (2''-CH₃), 21.88 (C-3); Mass (m/z) : 284 (90%), 283 (18%), 229 (41%), 163 (25%), 149 (12%), 135 (100%), 121 (14%), 107 (14%), 105 (10%), 77 (8.6%).

1-Benzoyl-2,2-bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)cyclopropane 11a :

Yield 28%, colorless thick liquid; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1670 (C=O), 1018 (cyclopropane); UV (λ_{max} , MeOH) : 237, 250, 278 nm; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 7.99 (2H, dd, J_{m} 1.5 Hz, J_{o} 7.8 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.59 (1H, tt, J_{m} 1.5 Hz, J_{o} 7.2 Hz, H-4'), 7.47 (2H, dt, J_{m} 1.5 Hz, J_{o} 7.8 Hz, H-3', 5'), 5.25

(1H, t, $J_{2''',1''}$ 7.5 Hz, H-2'''), 4.98 (1H, t, $J_{2'',1''}$ 6.9 Hz, H-2''), 2.55 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1), 2.31 (1H, dd, $J_{1''',a,2''}$ 7.5 Hz, J_{gem} 14.7 Hz, H_a -1'''), 2.23 (1H, dd, $J_{1''',b,2''}$ 7.5 Hz, J_{gem} 14.7 Hz, H_b -1'''), 2.18 (1H, dd, $J_{1'',a,2''}$ 6.9 Hz, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_a -1''), 2.06 (1H, dd, $J_{1'',b,2''}$ 6.9 Hz, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_b -1''), 1.78 (3H, s, 3'''-CH₃), 1.68 (3H, s, H-4'''), 1.57 (3H, s, 3''-CH₃), 1.50 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.54 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 4.5 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, H_a -3), 1.02 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 4.5 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.5 Hz, H_b -3); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CDCl_3) : 198.59 (C=O), 139.13 (C-1'), 133.97 (C-3'''), 132.77 (C-3''), 132.29 (C-4'), 128.33 (C-2', 6'), 128.06 (C-3', 5'), 122.06 (C-2'''), 120.97 (C-2''), 36.25 (C-1'''), 35.05 (C-1''), 30.51 (C-1), 28.30 (C-2), 25.91 (C-4'''), 25.71 (C-4''), 19.67 (C-3), 17.97 (3'''-CH₃), 17.85 (3''-CH₃); Mass (m/z) : 282 (71%), 281 (40%), 213 (31%), 177 (21%), 132 (100%), 105 (81%), 91 (8.5%).

2,2-Bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)-1-(4'-methylbenzoyl)cyclopropane 11b :

Yield 31%, colorless thick liquid; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1667.7 (C=O), 1019 (cyclopropane); UV (λ_{max} , MeOH) : 239, 255, 274 nm; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 7.90 (2H, d, J_{o} 8.1 Hz, H-2', 6'), 7.27 (2H, d, J_{o} 8.1 Hz, H-3', 5'), 5.25 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, $J_{2''',1''}$ 7.5 Hz, H-2'''), 4.98 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, $J_{2'',1''}$ 7.5 Hz, H-2''), 2.53 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1), 2.44 (3H, s, 4'-CH₃), 2.26 (1H, d, $J_{1''',2''}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1'''), 2.16 (1H, dd, $J_{1'',a,2''}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_a -1''), 2.06 (1H, dd, $J_{1'',b,2''}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_b -1''), 1.78 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, 3'''-CH₃), 1.67 (3H, s, H-4'''), 1.58 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 3''-CH₃), 1.54 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, H_a -3), 1.51 (3H, s, H-4''), 0.99 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.5 Hz, H_b -3); $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CDCl_3) : 198.01 (C=O), 142.79 (C-4'), 136.49 (C-1'), 133.71 (C-3'''), 132.54 (C-3''), 128.87 (C-2', 6'), 128.059 (C-3', 5'), 122.0 (C-2'''), 120.88 (C-2''), 35.75 (C-1'''), 34.94 (C-1''), 30.22 (C-1), 28.15 (C-2), 25.77 (C-4'''), 25.59 (C-4''), 21.44 (4'-CH₃), 19.30 (C-3), 17.82 (3'''-CH₃), 17.71 (3''-CH₃); Mass (m/z) : 296 (74%), 295 (34%), 227 (33%), 177 (18%), 146 (98.6%), 119 (100%), 105 (20%), 91 (22%), 77 (13.4%).

2,2-Bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)-1-(3'-methoxybenzoyl)cyclopropane 11c :

Yield 30%, colorless thick liquid; ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 1671 (C=O), 1041.4 (cyclopropane); UV (λ_{max} , MeOH) : 244, 275, 282, 301 nm; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) : 7.51 (1H, td, $J_{\text{m},0}$ 1.2,

7.8 Hz, H-6'), 7.42 (1H, dd, J_m 1.2, 2.7 Hz, H-2'), 7.29 (1H, t, J_o 7.8 Hz, H-5'), 7.21 (1H, dd, J_m 2.7 Hz, J_o 7.8 Hz), 5.15 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, $J_{2''',1''}$ 7.5 Hz, H-2'''), 4.90 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, $J_{2'',1''}$ 7.5 Hz, H-2''), 3.79 (3H, s, 3'-OCH₃), 2.44 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1), 2.18 (2H, d, $J_{1''',2''}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1'''), 2.07 (1H, dd, $J_{1''a,2''}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_a-1''), 1.99 (1H, dd, $J_{1''b,2''}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_b-1''), 1.68 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 3'''-CH₃), 1.58 (3H, s, H-4'''), 1.49 (3H, d, J 1.2 Hz, 3''-CH₃), 1.42 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.46 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, H_a-3), 0.93 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.5 Hz, H_b-3); $\delta^{13}C$ (CDCl₃) : 198.30 (C=O), 159.66 (C-3'), 140.53 (C-1'), 133.99 (3'''), 132.78 (C-3''), 129.31 (C-5'), 122.07 (C-2'''), 122.87 (C-2''), 120.81 (C-6'), 118.72 (C-4), 112.40 (C-2'), 55.40 (3'-OCH₃), 36.32 (C-1'''), 35.07 (C-1''), 30.61 (C-1), 28.29 (C-2), 25.89 (C-4'''), 25.73 (C-4''), 19.79 (C-3), 17.60 (3'''-CH₃), 17.86 (3''-CH₃); Mass (m/z) : 312 (88%), 311 (32%), 243 (22%), 162 (100%), 135 (100%), 107 (12%), 105 (20%).

2,2-Bis(3-methylbut-2-enyl)-1-(4'-methoxybenzoyl)cyclopropane 11d :

Yield 34%, colorless liquid; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 1663 (C=O), 1029.7 (cyclopropane); UV (ν_{max} , MeOH) : 231, 254, 260, 296 nm; δ_H (CDCl₃) : 7.90 (2H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.7, 9.0 Hz, H-2',6'), 6.87 (2H, dd, $J_{m,o}$ 2.7, 9.0 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.15 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, $J_{2''',1''}$ 7.5 Hz, H-2'''), 4.88 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, $J_{2'',1''}$ 7.2 Hz, H-2''), 3.81 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 2.41 (1H, dd, $J_{1,3a}$ 5.7 Hz, $J_{1,3b}$ 7.5 Hz, H-1), 2.20 (2H, d, $J_{1''',2''}$ 7.5, H-1'''), 2.05 (1H, dd, $J_{1''a,2''}$ 7.2 Hz, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_a-1''), 1.97 (1H, dd, $J_{1''b,2''}$ 7.2, J_{gem} 15.0 Hz, H_b-1''), 1.68 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 3'''-CH₃), 1.58 (3H, s, H-4'''), 1.49 (3H, d, J 1.5 Hz, 3''-CH₃), 1.41 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.43 (1H, dd, $J_{3a,3b}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3a,1}$ 5.7 Hz, H_a-3), 0.88 (1H, dd, $J_{3b,3a}$ 4.2 Hz, $J_{3b,1}$ 7.5 Hz, H_b-3); $\delta^{13}C$ (CDCl₃) : 196.97 (C=O), 162.93 (C-4'), 133.82 (C-1'), 132.65 (C-3'''), 132.22 (C-3''), 130.27 (C-2',6'), 122.16 (C-2'''), 121.05 (C-2''), 113.46 (C-3',5'), 55.42 (4'-OCH₃), 35.47 (C-1'''), 35.08 (C-1''), 30.10 (C-1), 28.32 (C-2), 25.92 (C-4'''), 25.75 (C-4''), 19.19 (C-3), 17.96 (3'''-CH₃), 17.84 (3''-CH₃); Mass (m/z) : 312 (91%), 311 (34%), 243 (20%), 162 (100%), 135 (100%).

Photolysis of substituted diallyl-benzoylcyclopropanes 6a-d and 11a-d :

A deoxygenated solution of benzoylcyclopropane **6a** (250 mg, 0.001 mol) was irradiated in methanol (100 ml) through Pyrex filtered light for 2 h under N₂ atmosphere, in Shrinivasan-Griffin photoreactor (> 300 nm). The solvent was removed under vacuum to get photolysate as thick liquid. The photolysate after chromatographic work up provided new compound **12a** as colorless oil (60%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 1 : 1). In spite of our best efforts, these *E*- and *Z*-isomers could not be separated.

The other diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes **6b-d** and **11a-d** were also photolysed by the same procedure. The compound **6b**, **11a** and **11b** on photolysis led to the formation of *E/Z* isomeric colorless oils of alkenes **12b** (52%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 1.1 : 1), **13a** (62%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 1.4 : 1) and **13b** (41%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 1.5 : 1) respectively. But, the diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes with methoxy group (i.e. **6c**, **6d**, **11c** and **11d**) did not undergo any photochemical change and thus furnished no alkenes (*E/Z*).

Compound 12a :

Yield 60%; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹), from mixture : 1684 (C=O).

δ_H (CDCl₃); *Z*-isomer : 7.88 (2H, dd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 7.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.49 (1H, tt, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 7.2 Hz, H-4'), 7.39 (2H, t, J_o 7.2, 7.5 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.70 (1H, s, H-5), 4.86 (1H, s, H_a-7), 4.83 (1H, s, H_b-7), 4.79 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.76 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 2.99 (2H, t, $J_{2,3}$ 7.8 Hz, H-2), 2.72 (2H, s, H-1''), 2.54 (2H, t, $J_{3,2}$ 7.8 Hz, H-3), 1.73 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 1.63 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃).

δ_H (CDCl₃); *E*-isomer : 7.88 (2H, dd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 7.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.49 (1H, tt, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 7.2 Hz, H-4'), 7.39 (2H, t, J_o 7.2, 7.5 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.78 (1H, s, H-5), 4.90 (1H, s, H_a-7), 4.83 (1H, s, H_b-7), 4.79 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.76 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 3.04 (2H, t, $J_{2,3}$ 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.89 (2H, s, H-1''), 2.39 (2H, t, $J_{3,2}$ 7.5 Hz, H-3), 1.76 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 1.65 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃).

Compound 12b :

Yield 52%; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹), from mixture : 1681 (C=O).

δ_H (CDCl₃); *Z*-isomer : 7.70 (2H, d, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.18 (2H, d, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.70 (1H, s, H-

5), 4.83 (1H, s, H_a-7), 4.78 (1H, s, H_b-7), 4.75 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.72 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 2.95 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.72 (2H, s, H-1''), 2.53 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.8 Hz, H-3), 2.33 (3H, s, 4'-CH₃), 1.74 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 1.62 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃).

δ_{H} (CDCl₃); *E*-isomer : 7.79 (2H, d, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.20 (2H, d, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.77 (1H, s, H-5), 4.85 (1H, s, H_a-7), 4.82 (1H, s, H_b-7), 4.75 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.72 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 2.99 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.89 (2H, s, H-1''), 2.36 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.8 Hz, H-3), 2.33 (3H, s, 4'-CH₃) 1.76 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 1.63 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃).

Compound 13a :

Yield 62%; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹), from mixture : 1683 (C=O).

δ_{H} (CDCl₃); *Z*-isomer : 7.89 (2H, dd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 7.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.49 (1H, tt, J_m 1.8 Hz, J_o 7.2 Hz, H-4'), 7.39 (2H, t, J_o 7.2, 7.5 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.97 (1H, br s, H-6), 5.93 (1H, br s, H-5), 5.08 (1H, d, J_{2'',1''} 6.3 Hz, H-2''), 2.98 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.82 (2H, d, J_{1'',2''} 6.3 Hz, H-1''), 2.48 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.5 Hz, H-3), 1.70 (3H, s, 7-CH₃), 1.69 (3H, s, H-8), 1.41 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.48 (3H, d, 3''-CH₃).

δ_{H} (CDCl₃); *E*-isomer : 7.87 (2H, dd, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 7.5 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.49 (1H, tt, J_m 1.5 Hz, J_o 7.2 Hz, H-4'), 7.39 (2H, dd/t, J_o 7.2, 7.5 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.97 (1H, br s, H-6), 5.93 (1H, br s, H-5), 5.19 (1H, d, J_{2'',1''} 6.9 Hz, H-2''), 3.02 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.92 (2H, d, J_{1'',2''} 6.9 Hz, H-1''), 2.42 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.5 Hz, H-3), 1.72 (3H, s, 7-CH₃), 1.66 (3H, s, H-8), 1.60 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.62 (3H, d, 3''-CH₃).

Compound 13b :

Yield 41%; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹), from mixture : 1683 (C=O), 1609 (C=C).

δ_{H} (CDCl₃); *Z*-isomer : 7.87 (2H, d, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.27 (2H, d, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 6.05 (1H, s, H-6), 6.01 (1H, s, H-5), 5.09 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, J_{2'',1''} 7.5 Hz, H-2''), 3.04 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.82 (2H, d, J_{1'',2''} 7.2 Hz, H-1''), 2.55 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.5 Hz, H-3), 2.42 (3H, s, 4'-CH₃), 1.76 (3H, s, 7-CH₃), 1.74 (3H, s, H-8), 1.70 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.63 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, 3''-CH₃).

δ_{H} (CDCl₃); *E*-isomer : 7.87 (2H, d, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-2',6'), 7.27 (2H, d, J_o 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 6.06 (1H, s, H-6),

6.03 (1H, s, H-5), 5.10 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 0.9 Hz, J_{2'',1''} 7.5 Hz, H-2''), 3.07 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.92 (2H, d, J_{1'',2''} 6.9 Hz, H-1''), 2.49 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.8 Hz, H-3), 2.42 (3H, s, 4'-CH₃), 1.82 (3H, s, 7-CH₃), 1.75 (3H, s, H-8), 1.71 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.66 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, 3''-CH₃).

Thermolysis of substituted diallyl-benzoylcyclopropanes 6a-d and 11a-d :

The compound **6a** (20 mg) was heated in a pyrex tube in a preheated silicon oil bath at 160 °C for 7 min. The tube was then taken out and reaction was quenched by cooling in cold water. Reaction mixture was analyzed by IR and 300 MHz ¹H NMR integrals which consisted of the starting compound 48% and the cleaved products **12a** (52%, an isomeric mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in the ratio of 2.0 : 1). The NMR and IR spectra of the compound **12a** obtained through thermal means overlapped with **12a** obtained photochemically.

Thermolysis of other diallyl-1-benzoylcyclopropanes, **6b-d** and **11a-d**, were also executed by the same procedure that yielded the respective products **12b** (42%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 2.0 : 1), **12c** (53%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 2.2 : 1), **12d** (35%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 2.3 : 1) and **13a** (95%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 3.5 : 1), **13b** (95%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 3.9 : 1), **13c** (95%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 3.3 : 1), **13d** (95%, a mixture of *E*- and *Z*-isomers in *E/Z* ratio = 4.0 : 1). The benzoylcyclopropanes **6c**, **6d**, **11c** and **11d** having methoxy group as the substituent remained unreacted upon photolysis but yielded the respective alkenes **12c**, **12d**, **13c** and **13d** upon thermolysis.

Compound 12c :

Yield 53%; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹), from mixture : 1682 (C=O), 1592 (C=C).

δ_{H} (CDCl₃); *Z*-isomer : 7.56-6.94 (4H, m, H-2',4',5',6'), 5.80 (1H, s, H-5), 4.89 (1H, s, H_a-7), 4.85 (1H, s, H_b-7), 4.83 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.81 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 3.80 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 3.10 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.82 (2H, s, H-1''), 2.65 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.5 Hz, H-3), 1.78 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 1.73 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃).

δ_{H} (CDCl₃); *E*-isomer : 7.56-6.94 (4H, m, H-2',4',5',6'), 5.87 (1H, s, H-5), 4.92 (1H, s, H_a-7), 4.89 (1H,

s, H_b-7), 4.83 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.81 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 3.83 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 3.12 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.99 (2H, s, H-1''), 2.49 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.5 Hz, H-3), 1.87 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 1.85 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃).

Compound 12d :

Yield 35%; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹), from mixture : 1677 (C=O), 1600.8 (C=C).

δ_H (CDCl₃); Z-isomer : 7.95 (2H, d, J₀ 8.1 Hz, H-2', 6'), 6.95 (2H, d, J₀ 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.79 (1H, s, H-5), 4.91 (1H, s, H_a-7), 4.89 (1H, s, H_b-7), 4.82 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.79 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 3.02 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.81 (2H, s, H-1''), 2.61 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.8 Hz, H-3), 3.89 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃) 1.86 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 1.80 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃).

δ_H (CDCl₃); E-isomer : 7.95 (2H, d, J₀ 8.1 Hz, H-2', 6'), 6.95 (2H, d, J₀ 8.1 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.87 (1H, s, H-5), 4.95 (1H, s, H_a-7), 4.93 (1H, s, H_b-7), 4.89 (1H, s, H_a-3''), 4.83 (1H, s, H_b-3''), 3.08 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.98 (2H, s, H-1''), 2.46 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.8 Hz, H-3), 3.89 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 1.82 (3H, s, 6-CH₃), 1.79 (3H, s, 2''-CH₃).

Compound 13c :

Yield 95%; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹), from mixture : 1685 (C=O).

δ_H (CDCl₃); Z-isomer : 7.55 (1H, dd, J_{m,0} 1.2, 8.1 Hz, H-6'), 7.51 (1H, dd, J_m 1.2, 1.8 Hz, H-2'), 7.38 (1H, t, J₀ 8.1, 8.1 Hz, H-5'), 7.12 (1H, dd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J₀ 8.1 Hz), 6.06 (2H, br s, H-5,6), 5.18 (1H, t, J_{2'',1''} 6.6 Hz, H-2''), 3.87 (3H, s, 3'-OCH₃), 3.07 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.82 (2H, d, J_{1'',2''} 6.6 Hz, H-1''), 2.56 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.5 Hz, H-3), 1.57-1.81 (12H, four singlets, 7-CH₃, H-8, H-4'', 3''-CH₃).

δ_H (CDCl₃); E-isomer : 7.55 (1H, td, J_{m,0} 1.2, 8.1 Hz, H-6'), 7.51 (1H, dd, J_m 1.2, 1.8 Hz, H-2'), 7.38 (1H, t, J₀ 8.1, 8.1 Hz, H-5'), 7.12 (1H, dd, J_m 1.8 Hz, J₀ 7.8 Hz), 6.09 (2H, br s, H-5,6), 5.10 (1H, t, J_{2'',1''} 6.9 Hz, H-2''), 3.87 (3H, s, 3'-OCH₃), 3.10 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.91 (2H, d, J_{1'',2''} 6.9 Hz, H-1''), 2.50 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.5 Hz, H-3), 1.79-1.82 (12H, four singlets, 7-CH₃, H-8, H-4'', 3''-CH₃).

Compound 13d :

Yield 95%; ν_{max} (cm⁻¹), from mixture : 1678 (C=O).

δ_H (CDCl₃); Z-isomer : 7.87 (2H, d, J₀ 9.0 Hz, H-2', 6'), 6.86 (2H, d, J₀ 9.0 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.96 (2H, br s, H-

5,6), 5.03 (1H, qt, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, J_{2'',1''} 6.9 Hz, H-2''), 3.80 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 2.94 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.5 Hz, H-2), 2.83 (2H, d, J_{1'',2''} 6.9 Hz, H-1''), 2.46 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.5 Hz, H-3), 1.70 (3H, s, 7-CH₃), 1.67 (3H, s, H-8), 1.62 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.58 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.5 Hz, 3''-CH₃).

δ_H (CDCl₃); E-isomer : 7.87 (2H, d, J₀ 9.0 Hz, H-2', 6'), 6.86 (2H, d, J₀ 9.0 Hz, H-3',5'), 5.96 (2H, br s, H-5,6), 5.03 (1H, qd, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, J_{2'',1''} 8.4 Hz, H-2''), 3.80 (3H, s, 4'-OCH₃), 2.97 (2H, t, J_{2,3} 7.8 Hz, H-2), 2.91 (2H, d, J_{1'',2''} 8.4 Hz, H-1''), 2.40 (2H, t, J_{3,2} 7.8 Hz, H-3), 1.73 (3H, s, 7-CH₃), 1.66 (3H, s, H-8), 1.61 (3H, s, H-4''), 1.56 (3H, d, J_{allyl} 1.2 Hz, 3''-CH₃).

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